

CLINICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL FEATURES OF COMMUNITY-HOSPITAL PNEUMONIA WITH PROLONGED COURSE IN CHILDREN

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Abstract. *The article presents the results of a retrospective analysis of 806 case histories of patients with community-acquired pneumonia hospitalized in 2023 in the pulmonology department of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Pediatrics.*

The results obtained indicate that community-acquired pneumonia with a protracted course is more common in young children, due to the influence of a burdened obstetric and gynecological history of mothers, an unfavorable background, as well as frequent respiratory infections and is clinically characterized by the presence of a prolonged cough, prolonged fever, decreased appetite, combined with physical changes in the lungs and a pronounced increase in CRP.

Keywords: *children, community-acquired pneumonia, clinical course, C-reactive protein, procalcitonin.*

Relevance. Despite significant advances in the diagnosis and treatment of bronchopulmonary pathology in children, the problem of community-acquired pneumonia (CAP) remains highly relevant, which is due to the high morbidity rate and relatively high mortality from this disease [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. In Russia, according to hospitalization data, the incidence of pneumonia is 5.3 per 1000 children aged 6 months - 5 years, and in economically developed countries, the incidence is 1.5–3 per 1000 children under 15 years of age and 3.4–6.8 in children under 5 years of age [6]. The mortality rate for community-acquired pneumonia in children under 5 years of age in developing countries can exceed 10%; in economically developed countries it is many times lower (up to 1%) [7].

Research in recent years indicates a significant change in the clinical course of the disease and an increase in the number of cases of prolonged pneumonia. When making a diagnosis of CAP, a combination of clinical and instrumental data is used. However, the paucity of physical symptoms of pneumonia and their similarity to those of ARVI, as well as incorrect interpretation of the obstructive syndrome, causes an erroneous diagnosis. The sensitivity of the combination of fever, tachypnea, local decreased breathing and wheezing for the diagnosis of pneumonia is about 94% [8, 9, 10, 11, 12].

Due to the low sensitivity and specificity of physical symptoms, WHO experts based the diagnosis of severe pneumonia on life-threatening signs (cyanosis, dehydration, impaired consciousness), and based the diagnosis of non-severe forms on tachypnea in the absence of obstruction [6, 7, 13].

In resource-limited settings, WHO recommends that children under 5 years of age with cough or difficulty breathing be diagnosed with pneumonia if they have tachypnea or chest indrawing on inspiration [7]. Russian experts believe that the diagnosis of CAP must necessarily include a chest x-ray [6, 14].

Despite a large number of studies concerning various aspects of pneumonia in childhood and the emergence of updated foreign guidelines for the management of children with CAP, many issues remain controversial and require solutions.

The purpose of the study was to study the features of the clinical course of community-acquired pneumonia with a prolonged course in children according to a retrospective analysis.

Material and methods. We conducted a retrospective analysis of 806 case histories of patients with community-acquired pneumonia hospitalized in 2023 in the pulmonology department of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Pediatrics. When analyzing case histories, clinical and anamnestic data, the presence of background and concomitant diseases, as well as laboratory data (blood test, level of C-reactive protein (CRP), procalcitonin (PCT)) and instrumental (chest x-ray, ultrasound of internal organs) were studied) research.

Statistical processing of the study results was carried out using the STATISTICA 10.0 application software package. For quantitative indicators, the arithmetic mean (M) and standard error of the mean (m) were calculated.

Results. According to a retrospective analysis of medical records, it was revealed that among 806 treated patients, acute community-acquired pneumonia prevailed in 525 (65.1%). The incidence of community-acquired pneumonia with a prolonged course was 281 (34.9%). The age of hospitalized children ranged from 4 months to 18 years.

Among children with community-acquired pneumonia with a protracted course, the greatest number were children of early and preschool age. Children of primary school age accounted for 8.2%, adolescent children (10-17 years old) -4% (Fig. 1).

Fig1. Frequency of community-acquired pneumonia with a prolonged course in children of different ages

The average duration of treatment for children in the hospital was 7 ± 2.1 days. The general condition of the patients on the day of admission was severe in 54% and moderately severe in 46% of children.

Important factors that determine the child's health and development are the characteristics of the obstetric history, the condition of the child at birth and its development before the onset of the present disease [6, 12].

A study of obstetric history showed that in 95% of mothers, pregnancy occurred against the background of anemia and in 83% of mothers with preeclampsia. Acute respiratory infections

and kidney diseases were reported in 18.7% of mothers. Anamnestic data showed that prolonged pneumonia is observed more often in premature and frequently ill children.

Among the diseases suffered, frequent respiratory infections and pneumonia were in first place, followed by bronchitis, obstructive bronchitis, bronchiolitis, and sinusitis. Among the background diseases, the presence of perinatal damage to the central nervous system and convulsive syndrome was revealed.

Upon admission to the hospital, the main complaints of parents of sick children were increased body temperature - in 85.5% (at the beginning of the disease) of children, prolonged cough - in 100%, shortness of breath - in 34.0%, runny nose - in 27%, loss of appetite - in 98.8%, lethargy – in 86.9%, sleep disturbance – in 45.5%. During an objective examination, shortness of breath of a mixed nature with the participation of auxiliary muscles in the act of breathing was present in 92.0% of patients. Percussion changes in the lungs were local in nature in the form of shortening of the pulmonary sound. On auscultation, harsh breathing, wet and dry rales, sometimes in combination with crepitus, were detected in all patients.

Determining the hemogram, CRP and PCT in a sick child can radically raise the level of diagnosis and treatment of community-acquired pneumonia and other bacterial infections [6, 14]. The results of laboratory tests revealed normal values of CRP in 96 (34%), and an increase in its level in 185 (66%). A study of procalcitonin levels showed high values in 18 (9.5%) patients.

Instrumental studies among children included chest radiography and magnetic resonance computed tomography (MRCT). Almost all children showed signs of pneumonia, and some showed signs of atelectasis and fibrotic changes in the lungs.

Conclusion. Community-acquired pneumonia with a protracted course is more common in young children, which is due to the influence of a burdened obstetric and gynecological medical history, external lanterns, as well as frequent respiratory factors and the nature of the disease, the presence of a prolonged cough, prolonged fever, decreased appetite, in combination with physical changes in the atmosphere and outdoors. a pronounced increase in CRP.

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